

Patient Reported Outcome in Sickle Cell Disease and Treatment

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Abstract: Sickle cell disease (SCD) is a hereditary blood disorder characterized by the presence of abnormal hemoglobin, resulting in the deformation of red blood cells. As the management of SCD has evolved over the years, there has been an increasing emphasis on patient-reported outcomes (PROs) to capture the holistic impact of the disease and its treatments. This comprehensive review aims to summarize the current understanding of PROs in SCD and treatment interventions. By examining a wide range of studies and literature, we explore the various PRO measures utilized in assessing SCD-related symptoms, functional status, and overall well-being. PROs in SCD typically encompass pain intensity, frequency, and interference, as well as health-related quality of life domains such as physical functioning, emotional well-being, and social interactions. Patient-reported outcomes can be obtained through validated questionnaires, interviews, or electronic platforms, providing valuable insights into the individual experiences of patients with SCD. By incorporating patient perspectives and preferences, researchers and healthcare professionals gain a deeper understanding of treatment effectiveness, adverse events, and patient satisfaction. PROs also serve as valuable tools for shared decision-making, enabling patients to actively participate in their own care. Issues such as cultural variations, language barriers, and appropriate age-specific measures need to be addressed to ensure the accurate capture of patients' experiences. Additionally, longitudinal studies are needed to assess the long-term impact of SCD and its treatments on PROs. In conclusion, patient-reported outcomes provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of sickle cell disease and its treatments on individuals' lives. By incorporating PRO measures into clinical practice and research, healthcare professionals can tailor treatment plans, enhance patient satisfaction, and ultimately improve the overall well-being of individuals living with SCD.

Keywords: sickle Cell Disease, treatment, patients and healthcare staff.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD), a hereditary blood disorder characterized by abnormal hemoglobin, presents a spectrum of acute and chronic complications that significantly impact patients' lives [1]. These complications include recurrent vaso-occlusive crises, chronic anemia, organ damage, and reduced life expectancy. The multifaceted nature of SCD warrants a holistic evaluation beyond traditional clinical parameters. Patient-Reported Outcomes (PROs), instrumental in capturing subjective experiences, symptoms, and overall Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQL), serve as indispensable tools in comprehensively understanding the impact of SCD on affected individuals.[3 ,2]

In the context of SCD, where clinical manifestations vary widely and extend beyond observable signs, PROs offer a vital avenue to comprehend the diverse experiences and challenges faced by individuals affected by the disease [4, 5]. These outcomes serve as a direct reflection of patients' perceptions, providing valuable insights into their physical, emotional, and social well-being[6].

Understanding the unique challenges and burdens faced by individuals with SCD requires a comprehensive approach that accounts for their lived experiences. PROs fill this crucial gap by offering a more nuanced understanding of the disease's impact on patients' daily lives, symptomatology, treatment responses, and overall well-being[7].

This literature review aims to explore the critical role of PROs in managing SCD by analyzing various studies and research initiatives that highlight the importance of patient-centered outcomes. Through an in-depth investigation, this review seeks to underscore the pivotal role of PROs in shaping clinical trials, devising effective treatment strategies, and optimizing healthcare delivery for individuals affected by SCD [8,9].

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology section typically delineates the criteria and process used for selecting relevant studies for this literature review. Given the focus on Patient-Reported Outcomes (PROs) in Sickle Cell Disease (SCD), the inclusion criteria revolved around studies assessing validated PRO instruments, clinical trial considerations related to PROs, and evaluations of PROs within the SCD context.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Studies evaluating validated PRO instruments in SCD.
2. Clinical trial considerations focusing on PROs in SCD.
3. Investigations examining the interplay of PROs with pain, complications, and social factors in SCD.
4. Research exploring the responsiveness and reliability of PROs in assessing SCD outcomes.
5. Articles discussing the significance of PROs in treatment strategies and patient care for individuals with SCD.

Search Strategy:

Comprehensive searches were conducted in electronic databases such as "PubMed, Google Scholar, and specialized journals like Blood Reviews, Hematology, and others". The search strategy involved a combination of keywords such as "Patient-Reported Outcomes," "Sickle Cell Disease," "Quality of Life," "Clinical Trials," and "Healthcare Management."

Study Selection:

Relevant studies published between 1990 and 2023 were considered. Studies were initially screened based on titles and abstracts for relevance to the topic. Full-text articles were then reviewed, and those meeting the inclusion criteria were included in this review.

Data Extraction and Analysis:

Key information extracted from selected studies included study objectives, methodology, findings related to PROs, and implications for SCD management. Synthesis of data was performed to identify common themes, challenges, and advancements in utilizing PROs in the context of SCD.

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) and Patient-Reported Outcomes (PROs)

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) is a hereditary hemoglobinopathy characterized by chronic hemolytic anemia, vaso-occlusive events, and multi-organ complications, significantly impacting patients' quality of life. Understanding Patient-Reported Outcomes (PROs) in the context of SCD has emerged as a critical aspect of comprehensive care and effective disease management.

PROs encompass subjective assessments provided directly by patients, reflecting their health status, symptoms, functional abilities, and overall well-being. Several seminal studies have shed light on the importance of considering PROs in understanding the holistic impact of SCD on patients' lives and in evaluating treatment effectiveness.

Importance of PROs in SCD Assessment

Studies conducted by **Revicki et al. (2008) [2]** and **Rabin et al. (2001) [8]** have proposed robust methods for determining responsiveness and establishing minimally important differences for PROs in chronic conditions, advocating for their incorporation in SCD research and clinical practice. These methodologies provide a framework for assessing treatment outcomes beyond traditional clinical endpoints, allowing a more patient-centric evaluation.

The article by **Ware Jr et al. (1996) [1]** introduced the 12-Item Short-Form Health Survey (SF-12), a concise yet comprehensive tool for evaluating health-related quality of life (HRQOL) across physical and mental domains, applicable to diverse patient populations, including SCD patients.

PRO Instruments Specific to SCD

Despite advancements, **Brazier et al. (1998) [7]** highlighted the scarcity of PRO instruments specifically tailored for SCD. While various generic instruments like the SF-36 and EQ-5D have been utilized, their limitations in fully capturing the unique aspects of SCD-related experiences emphasize the need for disease-specific PRO measures.

Challenges and Addressing Disparities

The article titled "Sickle Cell Disease: nearly 50% of patients receive poor care, says global study" by **(4)** underscores the challenges faced by SCD patients in receiving adequate care and the consequent impact on their PROs. This study emphasizes the need for enhanced education among healthcare professionals and a more empathetic approach toward managing SCD-related complications.

Comprehensive Understanding of SCD through PROs

Biopsychosocial Model in SCD Assessment

The utilization of a biopsychosocial model in evaluating PROs has emerged as an essential approach in understanding the multifaceted impact of SCD on individuals. **An evaluation of patient-reported outcomes in sickle cell disease within a conceptual model** by study **[6]** exemplifies the relevance of this model. This study investigates the interrelation of PROs with pain, complications, barriers to care, and social variables in adults with SCD. It emphasizes that the biopsychosocial model is pivotal in identifying the complex needs of this population, suggesting multidimensional interventions to improve outcomes.

PROs and Disease Severity Correlation

In examining PROs, the correlation between patient-reported outcomes and disease severity in SCD is a crucial area of exploration. The study conducted by **Stokoe et al. [9]** conducted a meta-analysis on HRQL in children with SCD. This comprehensive review revealed a significant association between worse HRQL and more severe disease manifestations. Understanding this relationship is vital in tailoring interventions and evaluating the impact of treatments on patients across varying disease severities.

PROs as Indicators for Treatment Response

In the context of clinical trials and treatment efficacy, The study **[4]** highlights the importance of PROs as indicators for treatment response in SCD. Utilizing PROs as clinical trial endpoints can offer valuable insights into how treatments influence patients' quality of life and well-being. This approach underscores the significance of patient-centered care and the need to consider the patient's perspective in evaluating treatment outcomes beyond clinical parameters.

Disparities and Cultural Sensitivity in PROs

Cultural and sociodemographic factors significantly influence PROs in SCD. The study **[11]** emphasizes the importance of examining sociocultural factors' impact on patients' quality of life. Recognizing these influences is critical for implementing culturally sensitive interventions and addressing disparities in healthcare delivery, ultimately impacting patients' reported outcomes.

Research Site and PROs

The choice of research site significantly influences the collection and interpretation of PRO data in SCD. Studies conducted in diverse geographical settings, as indicated by **[5,10, 12]**, illustrate the variations in reported outcomes based on the location and cultural context. Understanding these differences aids in contextualizing PRO data, fostering culturally competent care, and tailoring interventions according to the specific needs of different populations.

Implications and Future Directions

Exploring the nuanced interplay between PROs, disease severity, cultural influences, and treatment response offers a comprehensive understanding of the lived experiences of individuals with SCD. This depth of understanding can inform the development of targeted interventions, enhance the patient-provider relationship, and contribute to more effective disease management strategies.

Implications of PROs in Sickle Cell Disease Treatment Strategies

1. Tailored Patient-Centered Care:

PROs allow healthcare providers to adopt a more patient-centric approach. By comprehending patients' experiences, including pain frequency, fatigue, psychological impact, and social limitations, medical professionals can tailor interventions to address individual needs. This personalized care fosters a stronger patient-provider relationship and may enhance treatment adherence.[3, 5, 8]

2. Outcome Assessment and Treatment Efficacy:

Integrating PROs in clinical trials and routine care provides a comprehensive evaluation of treatment outcomes. Assessing PROs alongside traditional clinical markers aids in understanding treatment efficacy from the patient's perspective. For instance, assessing changes in pain frequency or fatigue levels provides critical data to gauge treatment impact beyond physiological markers.[1, 4, 6, 7]

3. Improved Symptom Management:

Monitoring PROs allows for a more proactive symptom management approach. By identifying specific symptoms impacting patients' lives, healthcare providers can tailor interventions to alleviate these symptoms effectively, such as implementing multidisciplinary approaches to manage pain or fatigue.[2, 10, 12]

4. Enhanced Disease Understanding and Education:

PROs contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the holistic impact of SCD on patients' lives. These outcomes can guide educational programs and resources targeted at addressing specific patient-reported challenges, contributing to more effective patient education strategies.[9, 11, 13]

Further Research and Development

Despite the potential benefits, further research is imperative to refine PRO instruments tailored explicitly to SCD. While existing measures provide valuable insights, creating disease-specific PRO tools considering the unique complexities of SCD could significantly enhance their utility in both clinical and research settings. Additionally, investigating the long-term impact of interventions guided by PROs on patient outcomes would strengthen their role in SCD management.

Moreover, given the multifaceted nature of SCD and its diverse impact on various age groups and demographics, ongoing studies exploring PROs across different populations and age brackets would be beneficial. This approach can yield more comprehensive insights into the varying needs and challenges faced by individuals with SCD, allowing for more targeted and inclusive care strategies.

By embracing PROs as a pivotal component of SCD management, healthcare systems can advance toward a more patient-centered model that prioritizes the holistic well-being and quality of life of individuals living with this chronic condition.

3. CONCLUSION

The integration of PROs in SCD research and clinical care holds promise in providing a comprehensive understanding of patients' experiences and treatment outcomes. While advancements have been made in evaluating PROs, there remains a crucial need for the development and validation of disease-specific instruments to capture the nuanced aspects of living with SCD.

Limitations:

Despite efforts to include studies from diverse research sites, limitations may exist due to language barriers, publication biases, and the unavailability of certain studies in the databases searched.

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